

National Idea and Legal Basis for the Development of Musical Culture of Youth

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Abstract

*“..We have a great history worth envying.
We have great ancestors worth envying. We have
incomparable riches and I believe that if we are lucky, we will
have a great future, great literature and art.” Shavkat Mirziyoev*

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Further development of Uzbek national musical art, study and restoration of the traditions of performing and creative schools, the heritage of great composers, singers and musicians on a deep scientific basis, promotion of our people to enjoy the best traditions of our musical heritage, national musical art of the younger generation through a broad acquaintance with them, their understanding of national identity consists of a number of tasks, such as the development of a sense of patriotism.

Keywords: Munojot, national musical art, cultural heritage,

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The development of national musical art began in the early years of independence and was enriched with a rich spiritual heritage. Our music is an educational tool with enormous impact. It is the nourishment of the soul that can give life force to the human psyche, heart and soul. Music, which has a powerful power, captures the human heart with its charm. National music is loved and understood only by those whose hearts are passionate about beauty. Simple "Munojot" (Arabic - begging, supplication) is performed in large Uzbek musical melodies, and people with beautiful hearts listen to it with love. Listening to and perceiving music is nurtured and absorbed from childhood.

It is impossible to talk about spiritual perfection without developing a sense of human beauty. Music is one of the powerful means of shaping and nurturing these delicate feelings. About the culture and art of music A. Karimov said, "When we talk about the spiritual maturity of man, of course, this goal cannot be achieved without the art of music ... The sounds of music, expressing the most noble, lofty and delicate human experiences, regardless of the people or nation." Because the aspects that show the greatness of a nation's existence are, first of all, its language, literature and art and culture, the historical and cultural heritage of the past.

In his address to the Oliy Majlis, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "In the implementation of the great tasks set before us, we must develop a national idea that will be a source of strength for us." On April 8, 2019, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop the concept of development of the national idea at a new stage of development of Uzbekistan" was issued. The adoption of this document has once again proved that "Spirituality, culture is the most effective weapon" and has armed the youth with a worthy ideology.

The national idea is the basis of youth education. If the national idea does not inspire the education of young people, today's education will not change. This was stated by President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev. "Today, the world's youth is the largest generation in the history of mankind, numbering 2 billion people. The future of our planet, its well-being depends on how our children grow up to be human beings. Our main task is to create conditions for young people to show their potential, to prevent the spread of the "virus" of violent ideas.

For this, we believe that it is necessary to develop multilateral cooperation in the field of social support of the younger generation, protection of their rights and interests "3. In today's renewed Uzbekistan, art has been freed from the bondage of communist ideology for many years. the foundations were laid. It should be noted that our national culture, national musical heritage and its history began to be introduced in the system of culture and art education as a special series of disciplines. education began to take its rightful place in the educational system. Music culture is closely connected with the radical reforms in the political, economic and social spheres, which are taking place in the life of the most recent period of independence.

It should be noted that during the years of independence, new opportunities have opened up for the development of music culture in Uzbekistan. Serious reforms have been carried out in the field of music art and music culture, and a number of positive indicators have been achieved. In order to develop the culture of traditional music, our state and government have adopted a number of decrees, developed measures and put them into practice. , festivals were organized.

In recent years, comprehensive measures have been taken in our country to raise the spiritual and educational level of our people, strengthen the material and technical base of cultural and art institutions, support the industry. The uniqueness of our national musical culture opens up a wide range of creative opportunities for today's youth. State youth policy, whether it wants to or not, is linked to the quality and effectiveness of education. You reap what you sow. This proverb of the people is not said in vain.

If the sense of keeping pace with the times, broad outlook, high knowledge, intellectual potential, creativity, involvement in the fate of the homeland does not move to the image of science and practice of our youth, the goal will remain the same. The adoption of five initiatives on this issue and the ongoing spiritual and educational work in this area are also focused on the problem of today's youth. Just as the whole thing-event is the key to its own idea, so the problems will have their own solutions. So culture is the key to education through speech, and education is through behavior.

This is one of the important criteria involved in uniting young people and increasing their intellectual abilities. In the age of globalization, it is expedient to introduce active and creative young people who can express themselves clearly and fluently, to introduce practical training courses to improve their leadership and moderation skills. It serves to strengthen the sense of cohesion and involvement of young people in the destiny of the country.

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